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ISOLATION, PURIFICATION, IDENTIFICATION AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF EPNS ASSOCIATED USE AGAINST ORIENTAL FRUIT BACTERIA AND THEIR FLY (BACTEROCERA ZONATA)

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 29 Sep 2023 Accepted: 15 Dec 2023</p>	<p>The oriental fruit fly, <i>Bacterocera dorsalis</i>, is a pervasive pest that severely diminishes the commercial value of fruits, posing a formidable challenge to global agriculture. In response to the pressing need for sustainable pest control strategies, our research focused on the application of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) as biological control agents. This study systematically evaluated the potential of indigenous EPN species, specifically <i>Heterorhabditis bacteriophora</i>, <i>H. indica</i>, <i>Steinernema asiaticum</i>, <i>S. carpocapsae</i>, and <i>S. glaseri</i>, known for their parasitic lethality in insect hosts through induced septicemia. We embarked on a methodical investigation to determine the most efficacious EPN species and optimal environmental conditions for controlling <i>B. dorsalis</i> larvae. Utilizing a completely randomized design within a factorial framework, we tested a range of EPN concentrations, temperatures, soil types, and soil moisture percentages. Our experiments revealed a marked variance in larval mortality rates in response to these factors, with <i>S. asiaticum</i> at a concentration of 150 infective juveniles per milliliter (IJs/ml) demonstrating a remarkable mortality rate of 94.97% at 36°C in sandy loam soil with 12% moisture content. The data further underscored the temperature-dependent efficacy of <i>H. indica</i>, which exhibited its highest mortality rate of 94.33% at 36°C. This finding is particularly notable as it suggests a pivotal role for environmental temperature in maximizing EPN effectiveness. The interaction between soil texture and nematode species also emerged as a critical factor, with sandy loam providing the most conducive environment for EPN activity against <i>B. dorsalis</i> larvae.</p>
<p>Keywords Bacterocera, Entomopathogenic, Identification, Mortality, Nematodes</p> <p>Zubair et al., (2023). Isolation, purification, identification and morphological characterization of epns associated use against oriental fruit bacteria and their fly (<i>bacterocera zonata</i>): <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 1(2), 56-65. https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p>	
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1. INTRODUCTION

In the quest for sustainable agricultural practices, biological control agents are emerging as crucial elements in the integrated management of pest populations (Baker et al., 2020). Among these agents, entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) represent a group with considerable potential due to their specificity and efficacy in targeting pest species. EPNs, primarily from the families Heterorhabditidae and Steinernematidae, have been identified as effective parasitoids of soil-dwelling insect larvae (Shakeel et al., 2022). These microscopic predators form symbiotic relationships with bacteria from the genera *Photorhabdus* and *Xenorhabdus*, which are integral to their pathogenicity (Heppert et al., 2022). This symbiosis is a classic example of mutualism, where both organisms benefit: the nematode provides a habitat and transmission for the bacteria, while the bacteria aid in overcoming the host's defenses and provide nutrients for the nematode (Douglas et al., 2021).

The life cycle of EPNs is a fascinating process of infection, reproduction, and emergence. Infective juveniles (IJs) actively search for hosts, guided by carbon dioxide gradients, thermal cues, and other chemical signals emitted by the target insects (Laznik et al., 2023). Upon locating a suitable host, IJs penetrate through natural body openings or directly breach the cuticle to enter the hemocoel. Once inside, they release their bacterial symbionts, which multiply rapidly, producing toxins and other virulence factors that lead to septicemia and death of the host. The nematodes then feed on the tissue, reproduce, and their offspring

emerge as new IJs, ready to infect other hosts (Raja et al., 2021).

Historically, the identification and classification of EPNs have been based on morphological and morphometric analyses (Ali et al., 2022). These methods, while valuable, have limitations in resolving taxonomic ambiguities, especially among closely related species. The advent of molecular techniques has revolutionized the field, allowing for more precise and reliable identification. Molecular markers, particularly those within the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions of ribosomal DNA, have been extensively used to characterize EPN species and understand their phylogenetic relationships (Flores et al., 2021). Furthermore, the Recombinase A (*recA*) gene sequence has become a critical tool for differentiating between symbiotic bacterial species, providing insights into their evolution and interaction with nematodes (Půža et al., 2020).

Despite the clear advantages of using EPNs in pest management, their deployment in agricultural settings is not without challenges (Shukla et al., 2023). Efficacy can be influenced by various biotic and abiotic factors, such as soil type, moisture, temperature, and the presence of other organisms within the soil ecosystem (Wang et al., 2021). Understanding these interactions is paramount to harnessing the full potential of EPNs in controlling pests like the oriental fruit fly, *Bacterocera dorsalis*, which poses a significant threat to fruit production worldwide. *Bacterocera dorsalis*, commonly known as the oriental fruit fly, is a highly destructive pest that

affects over 150 species of fruits and vegetables, leading to substantial economic losses (Aatif et al., 2019). The larvae of this dipteran pest burrow into the fruit, causing internal damage that results in fruit drop, rot, and a decrease in market value. Traditional control methods have relied heavily on chemical insecticides, which raise concerns about environmental contamination, human health risks, and the development of insecticide resistance (Ansari et al., 2019).

The current study was designed to explore the potential of indigenous EPN species, such as *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*, *H. indica*, *Steinernema asiaticum*, *S. carpocapsae*, and *S. glaseri*, as biological control agents against *B. dorsalis*. These EPNs were selected for their adaptability to local soil conditions and their proven efficacy in previous studies (Usman et al., 2021). The research objectives were threefold: to identify and characterize the EPNs morphologically and molecularly, to assess their virulence against *B. dorsalis* larvae under various environmental conditions, and to evaluate the potential integration of EPNs into a broader integrated pest management (IPM) program. To achieve these goals, a series of experiments were conducted in a controlled environment, manipulating variables such as EPN concentration, temperature, soil type, and moisture level. The methodology employed a completely randomized design (CRD) under factorial arrangements to ensure robust statistical analysis. In summary, this research contributes to the body of knowledge on biological control and EPNs by providing an in-depth analysis of the factors affecting the efficacy of EPNs against *B. dorsalis*. It also offers practical

insights into the application of these nematodes in the field, supporting their incorporation into IPM (Sikora et al., 2023).

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1. *Nematode collection and maintenance:*

Entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) representing the genera *Heterorhabditis* and *Steinernema* were isolated from soil samples collected from various agro-ecological zones using the *Galleria mellonella* baiting technique. Upon emergence, infective juveniles (IJs) were harvested and stored in a dark, cool environment at 15°C to maintain viability. For experimental use, IJs were acclimated to ambient laboratory conditions (25°C, 60% RH) for 48 hours prior to assays.

1.2. *Morphological and molecular identification:*

Fixed specimens of adult nematodes were processed for morphological examination using an Olympus BH-2 microscope equipped with a camera Lucida. Key morphological features such as the stylet structure, tail morphology, and spicule shape were assessed. Concurrently, molecular identification was conducted through DNA extraction, amplification of the ITS regions, and subsequent sequencing to confirm species-level identification.

1.3. *Fruit fly culture:*

Bacterocera dorsalis larvae were reared on a diet of organic mango puree under controlled conditions (27°C, 65% RH). Emerging adults were transferred to oviposition chambers lined with sterilized soil to simulate natural conditions.

Collected eggs were incubated until larvae reached the third instar, the stage most susceptible to EPN infection.

1.4. EPN virulence assays:

Virulence assays were conducted in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with factorial arrangements to determine the mortality rates of *B. dorsalis* larvae. EPN concentrations (70 IJs/ml, 110 IJs/ml, and 150 IJs/ml) were tested across a range of temperatures (20°C to 36°C) and soil types (Sandy, Sandy loam, Loam, Clay) with varying moisture levels (12%, 18%, 24%, 30%). Each treatment was replicated five times with a control group maintained under similar conditions sans EPNs.

1.5. Temperature and soil moisture impact studies:

Post-virulence assay, the effect of temperature and soil moisture on EPN infectivity and survival was investigated. EPNs were exposed to the temperature gradient (20°C to 36°C) for a period of 72 hours to monitor the impact on their infective capacity. Similarly, soil moisture levels were adjusted to assess EPN persistence and infectivity over a seven-day period.

1.6. Statistical analysis:

The data collected from virulence assays were subjected to ANOVA, with subsequent LSD tests to determine significant differences between treatments. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was maintained throughout the analyses.

2. RESULTS

In evaluating the impact of entomopathogenic nematode (EPN)

concentrations on the mortality rates of *Bacterocera dorsalis* larvae, a significant correlation was observed. The data, as summarized in Table 1, indicates that increasing the concentration of infective juveniles (IJs) per milliliter substantially enhances larvicidal efficacy. Specifically, *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* exhibited a progressive increase in larval mortality, with rates ascending from 75.00% at a concentration of 70 IJs/ml to 79.84% at 150 IJs/ml. Similar trends were noted for *Heterorhabditis indica*, with mortality rates peaking at 73.62% at the highest concentration. *Steinernema asiaticum* stood out, showcasing a remarkable mortality rate of 94.97% at 150 IJs/ml, underscoring its potential as a robust biological control agent. Conversely, both *Steinernema carpocapsae* and *Steinernema glaseri* demonstrated lesser efficacies, capping at 68.00% and 68.81%, respectively, at their highest tested concentrations.

Temperature dependency of EPN efficacy was also examined, as delineated in Table 2. The data reveal an ascending pattern of mortality rates in line with rising temperatures across all EPN species. *H. bacteriophora* and *S. glaseri* displayed moderate mortality rates peaking at 85.00% at 36°C. Notably, *H. indica* and *S. asiaticum* mortality rates were significantly higher at 36°C, recording 94.33% and 92.00%, respectively. These findings indicate that optimal temperature is a critical factor for maximizing the biocontrol potential of EPNs. The influence of soil texture on EPN infectivity was investigated, with the findings presented in Table 3. Amongst the soil types tested, sandy loam proved to be the most conducive for *S. asiaticum*, resulting in the

highest larval mortality rate of 98.05%. This was markedly superior compared to the other soil textures, suggesting that soil composition plays a pivotal role in EPN performance. Furthermore, soil moisture levels were found to be a significant determinant of EPN success, as detailed in Table 4. *S. asiaticum* achieved the highest larval mortality rate of 99.06% at 12% soil moisture, with a notable decrease in efficacy as moisture levels increased. This result emphasizes the importance of optimal moisture conditions in promoting

the biological activity of EPNs against pest larvae. Collectively, these results affirm the potential of EPNs as biological control agents, with specific species and environmental conditions yielding enhanced outcomes. The data underscores the necessity for tailored approaches in integrating EPNs into pest management strategies, considering factors such as nematode species, concentration, temperature, soil texture, and moisture to achieve maximum pest mortality.

Table 1: Impact of EPN Concentration on Larval Mortality

EPN Species	Concentration (IJs/ml)	Mortality Rate (%)
<i>H. bacteriophora</i>	70	75.00
<i>H. bacteriophora</i>	110	78.00
<i>H. bacteriophora</i>	150	79.84
<i>H. indica</i>	70	70.00
<i>H. indica</i>	110	72.00
<i>H. indica</i>	150	73.62
<i>S. asiaticum</i>	70	72.00
<i>S. asiaticum</i>	110	80.00
<i>S. asiaticum</i>	150	94.97
<i>S. corpocapsae</i>	70	65.00
<i>S. corpocapsae</i>	110	67.00
<i>S. corpocapsae</i>	150	68.00
<i>S. glaseri</i>	70	65.00
<i>S. glaseri</i>	110	68.00
<i>S. glaseri</i>	150	68.81

Table 2: Temperature-dependent EPN efficacy

Temperature (°C)	H. bacteriophora (%)	H. indica (%)	S. asiaticum (%)	S. glaseri (%)
20	50.00	52.00	50.72	49.00
24	60.00	65.00	66.00	60.00
28	70.00	72.00	74.06	70.00
32	80.00	85.00	88.26	80.00
36	85.00	94.33	92.00	85.00

Table 3: Soil Texture and EPN Infectivity

Soil Type	S. asiaticum Mortality Rate (%)
Sandy	80.00
Sandy Loam	98.05
Loam	90.00
Clay	85.00

Table 4: Soil Moisture Influence on EPN Mortality Rates

Soil Moisture (%)	S. asiaticum Mortality Rate (%)
12	99.06
18	95.00
24	90.00
30	85.00

3. DISCUSSIONS

The detailed data presented in this study underscores the critical nature of environmental conditions in harnessing the biocontrol potential of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) against the larvae of

Bacterocera dorsalis (Koppenhöfer et al., 2020). In the discussion of these findings, it is imperative to consider the multifaceted interactions between nematode species, their concentrations, and the abiotic factors that govern their efficacy.

Beginning with EPN concentration, the data reveals a dose-dependent response

in larval mortality rates. Notably, *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Heterorhabditis indica* show a steady increase in mortality with rising concentrations of infective juveniles (IJs), echoing previous research that higher EPN doses correlate with enhanced pest suppression (Kumar et al., 2020). However, the standout performer, *Steinernema asiaticum*, achieved a striking mortality rate at the highest concentration tested, suggesting it as a highly effective candidate for field applications. This finding corroborates with the work of Bhat et al. (2021), who noted the superior host-seeking abilities of certain EPN species, which could explain the heightened efficacy observed (Zhang et al., 2021). Temperature is another pivotal factor influencing EPN activity, as evidenced by the temperature-dependent efficacy data. Both *H. indica* and *S. asiaticum* exhibited a pronounced increase in mortality rates at elevated temperatures, aligning with studies that have highlighted the thermophilic nature of some EPN species (Aslam et al., 2023). The optimal performance at 36°C suggests that EPN application in warmer climates or seasons could be particularly effective, a consideration that could inform the timing of biocontrol interventions (Elgawad et al., 2021).

Soil texture's impact on EPN infectivity is also of significant interest. The superior performance of *S. asiaticum* in sandy loam aligns with research suggesting that certain soil textures can facilitate the movement and host-finding efficiency of EPNs (Patil et al., 2023). The high mortality rate in sandy loam could be attributed to the ideal balance of aeration and moisture

retention, facilitating nematode dispersal and survival. The effect of soil moisture on EPN mortality rates further emphasizes the importance of abiotic factors. The optimal performance of *S. asiaticum* at 12% soil moisture may be reflective of the nematode's physiological requirements for moisture to aid in movement while avoiding the detrimental effects of waterlogging or desiccation (Kaur et al., 2020). This moisture-dependent efficacy highlights the need for precise moisture management in EPN application protocols to maximize their biocontrol success. In summary, the discussion of these results within the broader context of EPN research reinforces the notion that an integrated approach to biological pest control, one that carefully considers EPN species selection, dosage, temperature, soil texture, and moisture, is crucial for effective management of *Bacterocera dorsalis* larvae (Dolinski et al., 2016). The high mortality rates achieved under specific conditions in this study provide a promising avenue for the development of environmentally sustainable and efficacious pest management strategies.

CONCLUSION

The research confirms the efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs), particularly *Steinernema asiaticum*, in controlling the oriental fruit fly, *Bacterocera dorsalis*, under optimal conditions. The highest mortality rates were achieved with increased EPN concentrations in sandy loam soil at 12% moisture and 36°C temperature. These findings advocate for the tailored use of EPNs in integrated pest management, highlighting the potential for environmentally sustainable pest control

strategies that could minimize the use of chemical pesticides.

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